

Strategic Vigilance and its Role in Entrepreneurial Performance: An Analytical Study of the Views of a Sample of Managers in the Ur Company in Nasiriyah, Iraq

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 10,2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 23,2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Strategic vigilance, Entrepreneurial Performance.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4427459</p>	<p><i>The study aims to demonstrate the impact of strategic vigilance in its dimensions related to (technological vigilance, marketing vigilance, competitive vigilance, and environmental vigilance) of managers in the Ur public company on Entrepreneurial performance in its dimensions represented by (strategic orientation, resource orientation, management structure, rewards philosophy, and entrepreneurial culture)). As for the study sample, it included a sample of (123) managers in that company. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive and analytical approach was used. The questionnaire consisted of (37) items was used as a main tool for collecting study data through the use of global measures of the main variables of the study, and a number of statistical methods and methods were used to analyze the study variables and test hypotheses. After conducting the statistical analysis process of the study data and its hypotheses, it reached a number of results, most notably the presence of a significant effect of strategic vigilance with its dimensions on the entrepreneurial performance in its dimensions, as well as one of the most prominent conclusions of the study was that the departments of the Iraqi public company Ur give clear attention to the requirements of strategic alertness of all kinds. The study recommended that the company should use a modern information system with advanced technologies capable of collecting data related to customers and updating them continuously to support decision-makers with information that enhances the state of alertness, caution and attention to them and interpreting weak signals coming from the environment at all times with high accuracy.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Management science is distinguished from other social sciences by its vitality and openness to the rest of the fields of science and knowledge and its various branches, and at the same time the great overlap and intermingling between the various branches of management science and its specializations, and based on this fact the idea of this study came to mix between one of the important topics in the field of strategic management, which is The topic of strategic vigilance in organizations, with one of the vital topics that all organizations aspire to in their work, except that of pioneering performance. As the organizations themselves live in the results of complex and highly competitive globalization, in addition to being an open system that takes from the environment its inputs and gives its outputs to it. Among the deteriorating and dead organizations.

Strategic vigilance has become an urgent necessity and has an effective role in providing the necessary information about the various elements of the organization's business environment, about competitors, customers, technology and in many aspects: products, strategies, technologies used, and in general everything that affects competition, and then adopting its activities And to benefit from them in improving their entrepreneurial performance, as organizations wishing to achieve leadership seek to possess pioneering performance, which refers in its components to strategic practices that determine future directions for the activities of the organization. The risks associated with uncertainties and new business adventures leading to the renewal of strategic capabilities, which enable these organizations to acquire the essential capabilities and organizational resources towards the desired entrepreneurial behavior, noting that this behavior confirms the organization of the mechanism by which these organizations operate, whether economic, social, technological or other .

First: The Scientific Methodology of the Study

1. study problem and its questions

Contemporary organizational thought developed, especially in the mid-nineties of the last century and the beginning of the current century, with a number of contemporary and modern issues imposed by the business environment, creativity, rapid changes, and competition to provide better products and services. Entrepreneur),

and despite the research efforts in interpreting these scientific topics, their contents and their analysis, there are a number of cognitive issues and behavioral skills that still need further research and investigation. The study problem includes a number of research questions that seek to provide an answer to them through the knowledge and experimental contents coming to the study, and these questions are as follows:-

- What is the level of implementation of the dimensions of strategic Vigilance in the Ur public company from the view of the study sample individuals?
- What is the level of evaluation of the study sample individuals for the dimensions of the entrepreneurial performance in the Ur public company?
- What is the relationship and influence between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the dimensions of entrepreneurial performance in the Ur State Company?
- How do the dimensions of strategic vigilance affect the dimensions of the entrepreneurial performance in the UR public company?

2. study goals

Based on the problem and the research gap in the above, the current study aims mainly to “demonstrate the impact of the dimensions of strategic vigilance on the dimensions of the company's entrepreneurial performance from the managers' point of view in it by achieving the following goals:

- Identify the level of application of the dimensions of strategic vigilance in the company from the viewpoint of the study sample.
- Identify the level of the study sample's dimensions of the company's leadership performance dimensions.
- Determine the relationship between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the dimensions of entrepreneurial performance in the company.
- Determine the impact of the dimensions of strategic vigilance on the dimensions of the company's leadership performance.

3. importance of studying

The study derives its importance by addressing the studied topics and the extent of their application and employment in organizations operating in the industrial sector to study and analyze their concepts, objectives and scientific importance to achieve high levels of entrepreneurship and performance compared to other organizations.

4. Hypothesis study model

The hypothetical study model was based on what came from a survey of the intellectual findings of the solid scientific literature related to the topics of strategic awakening and pioneering performance. After conducting a broad review of recent research in this field, a hypothetical outline of the study was formulated to show the dimensions and variables of the researched phenomenon represented by the study problem and its intellectual premises, which stipulated the impact of strategic vigilance on the pioneering performance of the public company.

2. $H_0:1.2$: There is no statistically significant association between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the dimension of resource orientation.
3. $H_0:1.3$: There is no statistically significant association between the dimensions of strategic vigilance, and the dimension of management structure.
4. $H_0:1.4$: There is no statistically significant correlation between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the reward philosophy dimension.
5. $H_0:1.5$: There is no statistically significant association between the dimensions of strategic vigilance, and the dimension of entrepreneurial culture.

Second main hypothesis:

There is no statistically significant effect of strategic vigilance in terms of its dimensions (technological vigilance, marketing vigilance, competitive vigilance, environmental vigilance), on the pioneering performance and its dimensions in the Ur public company. Five sub-hypotheses are divided into this hypothesis:

1. $H_0: 2.1$: There is no statistically significant effect between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the dimension of strategic direction.
2. $H_0: 2.2$: There is no statistically significant effect between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the dimension of resource orientation.
3. $H_0: 2.3$: There is no statistically significant effect between the dimensions of the strategic vigilance, and the management structure dimension.
4. $H_0: 2.4$: There is no statistically significant effect between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the reward philosophy dimension.
5. $H_0: 2.5$: There was no statistically significant effect between the strategic vigilance dimensions and the entrepreneurial culture dimension.

6. Study limits

The borders of the current study, including the following:

- a) Human boundaries: It is represented in a sample consisting of (123) from (managers of the Ur public company in the city of Nasiriyah in Iraq.
- b) Spatial boundaries: (Ur General Company laboratories in the city of Nasiriyah in Iraq)
- c) Scientific boundaries: The study was scientifically defined by what stated its objectives, importance, and questions.
- d) Temporal boundaries: The time period that took to complete the study, is the period from 1/8/2020 until 1/11/2020.

Second: Strategic Vigilance

Strategic vigilance is one of the new methods in modern management science, as it contributes to bringing organizations closer to the various stakeholders. From this, the importance of adopting a system of vigilance and auditing has emerged in the process of monitoring the organization's environment to ensure more control over the information system. And strategic alertness is described as the sense of sight and hearing of the organization, as it is the surveillance radar at all times and in all directions to track useful information (Arnaud, 2012: 1). As for (Fayrouz, al-Zahraa, 2015: 8), he defines strategic vigilance as an organized method in management in the strategic management of the organization, focusing on the competitive aspect, processing information and knowing useful information to control the periphery of the organization (opportunities and threats). As for (Khalifa Ahmed, 2015: 46), he defined it as the continuous collective process, which is carried out by a group of individuals in a voluntary manner, and they track and then use the expected information regarding the changes that are likely to occur in the external environment of the organization, with the aim of creating business opportunities and reducing General notification and uncertainty. While (Bouarawi, Melody, 2017: 6) defined it as the activity that enables us to stay informed of all developments in the sector that we occupy. (Ghalib, Malika, 2012: 158) shows the process of searching for information on a continuous and continuous basis, whether this information is strategic, social, political, scientific, technological, or specific to the institution's environment and all its variables, opportunities and dangers. While (Al-Maliki, Helen, 2016: 50), he defined it as the methods used by the organization to reach the goals and objectives putted. (Lamine, Omar, 2017: 5) showed that strategic vigilance is to inquire about competitors' behaviors, technological innovations, monitor commercial strategies, and know the new desires of consumers, and in general, monitor the environment. All these activities are part of the strategic vigilance that aids in organizing the tasks of information observation, testing, interpretation and dissemination with the aim of improving important decisions in the organization.

The importance of strategic vigilance is demonstrated by the fact that it allows financial vigilance to achieve abundance because the information gathered has the ability to improve the product's technical characteristics and quality and reduce its cost. Strategic vigilance allows for a good passage of information across various organizational levels in the organization. Its importance is also evident from the fact that it is considered a strategic means of management (Medawar, 2013: 81).

Strategic vigilance aims to create opportunities and avoid situations of uncertainty, especially when reducing the imbalances that may occur in the development of their social, economic, and technological environment. Vigilance is comprehensive, that is, it is technological, commercial, competitive, and informational, but these four types can be called strategic awakening (El-Yameen Valte, 2006: 12).

Dimensions of Strategic Vigilance

Most specialists and researchers agree, such as (Brouard, 2000: 4), (Dumas et al, 2004: 5-6), (Isabelle, 2008: 2), (M., Akli, 2008: 17), (Lamia, 2009: 21) and (Grine, 2010: 12) stated that there are four dimensions of strategic awakening, which are:

1. Technology Vigilance

Technological vigilance refers to what the organization does in terms of monitoring and analyzing the scientific and technological environment in order to identify opportunities and threats. It allows the organization to know new technologies related to its work activity and works to enhance competitiveness in the event of its exploitation by acquiring technological innovations (patents) by transferring and using scientific and technological information to create Positive changes in products, methods and production methods. Thus, it seeks to achieve advantages in production that surpass its competitors in the market. Technological change creates both opportunities, as organizations begin to discover how to use technology to create new products, and threats that must re-think their technological strategies (Jakobiak, 2012: 1). This means that technological change creates threats for some organizations and opportunities for others. Therefore, organizations should monitor this change regularly and continuously in order to adapt to it in the future (Barney & Hesterly, 2006:35).

2. Marketing vigilance

Research, processing and publication of information related to the organization's market. This kind of vigilance is based on following up: market developments, consumers' market, competitors (Marnat Christophe, 2009: 4). Marketing vigilance is the availability of information for the leaders of the organization that helps them better understand the emerging markets and trends in the immediate environment of the sector in which they operate, and the challenge facing any organization lies in its social importance, so marketing managers must keep pace with emerging social trends and consumers' desires and tendencies through the vigilance process that provides them with wealth. Of the information that is collected and then processed and converted into useful information, and most importantly, it is distributed within the organization so that they are ready to serve specific marketing activities, i.e. orientation to the market, and this is positively related to the performance of the organization. Useful information is an approach to decision-making, "good vigilance is the basis for good marketing decisions" through the use of information produced by vigilance, and it has a contribution to influence marketing management strategies (Lewis & Chambers, 2000: 588).

3. Competitive vigilance

It is the search, processing and publication of information related to the competitor of the organization, that is, related to the monitoring of direct and indirect competitors, current and potential. It monitors competitors' strategy, pricing policy, and financial results (Khalifa Ahmed, 2015: 47). He adds (Helmy, 2009: 22-23), who indicated that competitive awakening aims to know the following:

- Real potentials and capabilities of competitors.
- Competitors' performance and strategies and knowledge of their news.
- The skills and competence of current competitors.
- Assumptions and decisions made by competitors.
- Actions that the competitor cannot do.

4. Environmental vigilance

Environmental vigilance seeks vigilance and continuous monitoring by collecting information related to all environmental events and developments that occur to organizations and their surroundings. The implementation of environmental vigilance is a difficult task for organizations, and since it concerns a wide aspect of the environment, the organization must deal with the information with great care in terms of analyzing, processing and sending it to decision-makers so that they in turn determine the basic information in the vigilance process (Al-Maliki Helen, 2016: 56).

Third: Entrepreneurial performance

Entrepreneurial performance is related to the administrative structure, rewards, entrepreneurial culture, strategic orientation and resource orientation. The important challenges facing the economic, cultural and social situation in the twenty-first century call for the achievement of pioneering performance by organizations. In the dynamic environment, all organizations regardless of their size and age resort to seeking To search for modern and contemporary methods consistent with developments in the external environment, and to keep pace with modern administrative concepts and to move towards continuously satisfying customers' needs and achieving competition and exclusivity from other organizations, organizations must work to raise their level of performance to reach leading performance (Rankin, 2014: 43) . Berninger (2004: 3) is defined as the pioneering

performance that provides the ability for an organization to achieve its strategic objectives of permanent financing, customer service, improvement of internal processes, and education and growth of the organization. As for (Callaghan & Venter, 2011: 32), entrepreneurial performance is defined as a combination of returns and satisfaction in a framework of distinction, exclusivity and risk.

Regarding the importance of entrepreneurial performance, Kuhhal (2003: 2) points out that the importance of entrepreneurial performance is evidenced by being performance based on the common ideal working language based on setting goals, identifying work problems, and continuing to focus on the work method to identify critical points in it as well as pressure points. And the performance evaluation according to the high performance standards set. (Agca et al, 2008: 231-232) considers that the leading performance of countries is an important source of income, or an important resource in the economic decision.

Entrepreneurial performance Dimensions

The researcher relied on the dimensions adopted by (Karimi, Abbas, et al, 2012: 2275), which were represented by (strategic orientation, resource orientation, management structure, rewards philosophy, entrepreneurial culture), and the reason for choosing these dimensions is due to the fact that they are compatible with The nature of the study and the organization studied on the one hand, and on the other hand, that most researchers had a prior agreement on these dimensions (Fox, Julie M., BS, MBA, 2005), (Boberg, Katarina et al, 2005), (Dyduch, Wojciech, 2008). , (Majid, Izaidin Abdul, 2011).

1. Strategic Orientation

This dimension clarifies that strategies in their nature describe the strategic direction and what are the factors that drive them in the formation of the strategy, and that the corporate strategy is led by the opportunities in the environment and not the resources required to exploit these opportunities, and since the opportunities are driven by the strategy, therefore, any opportunity is important to the company, once it is completed. Diagnosing the opportunity, then one must organize the resources required to exploit it (Brown, 2001: 6).

2. Resource Orientation

The orientation towards resources to exploit opportunities initially consists of a specific commitment to resources. The company with a pioneering administrative orientation tries to amplify the formation of value by exploiting opportunities and at the same time reducing the required resources, especially the company's resources, and the organizations are pioneering or gaining new knowledge of resources or anchor assets Through the use of creative methods, and knowledge resources include different types such as procedures, market, or technology, entrepreneurial knowledge consists of using resources that have not been used correctly. Organizations at the present time use federation, integration and networks to obtain markets, information, technology and other resources very important for creativity and use of strategies. Organizational Entrepreneurship (Chirani, Ebrahim, 2013: 67-68).

3. Management Structure

The structure in organizations is usually in the form of a number of vertical levels between the executive directors and the staffing staff at the lower level has a small space of freedom, and written job descriptions of all the staffs in the organization are present, and the non-management employees receive instructions and procedures and develop them, and the top level managers help them in Definition and description of data (Chirani, Ebrahim, 2013: 67-68).

4. Reward Philosophy

The organization of the reward philosophy is very important for corporate behavior, so that the founder is interested in creating and obtaining wealth (value) as a result of that, entrepreneurial companies tend to make the compensation or reward base according to how individuals contribute to the creation of value. The organization's structure in this type of company helps to evaluate because it is designed for activities. Independent and independent responsibility of employees, trustee companies are managed according to traditional administrative growth and tend to make this compensation or bonus related to the amount of resources that the individual controls or supervises (such as physical assets, individuals ... etc) and the administrative position. If the individual is successful then he is promoted to a position that oversees more resources (Brown, 2001: 7-8).

5. Entrepreneurial Culture

Culture in its general sense clarifies the meanings, symbols, and complex assumptions about good or not good, legitimate, or illegal things, which fall under the prevailing practices and norms in society (Licht & Siegel, 2006: 8). Confirms (Wheelen & Hunger, 2004: 290) that in order to create a more innovative organization, the senior management to work on the development of entrepreneurial culture, embodied in the openness to the aspects of new technologies and transfer to the activities of the organization and the type of goods and services provided by outstanding flexibility between the types of Change, and willingness to accept any percentage of failure.

Fourthly: Analyze study data

In this section, the levels of the research dimensions and variables in the researched company will be identified through the arithmetic mean and the standard deviation, and at the same time the correlations between the

research dimensions and variables will be identified, and the extent of consistency of the research paragraphs will be identified according to the answer of the surveyed sample and the extent of the scale stability Through factor analysis, as well as analysis of influence hypotheses.

First: Descriptive analysis of the research dimensions and variables and correlation coefficients:

The research consists of two independent variables, the first is strategic vigilance and the follow-up is entrepreneurial performance (EP), as strategic vigilance consists of four dimensions (technology vigilance (TV), competitive vigilance (CV), marketing vigilance (MV), environmental vigilance (EV)). Entrepreneurial performance consists of five dimensions, namely (strategic Orientation (SO), resource orientation (RO), management structure (MS), reward philosophy (RP), entrepreneurial culture (EC)). Table () will display the statistical description of the research dimensions and its variables. The arithmetic mean and the standard deviation for each of them will be summarized and any dimension or variable that gets a hypothetical mean higher than (3) is acceptable and vice versa, then the extent of the relationship of the dimensions and variables with each other will be shown through the correlation coefficient.

Table (1) Descriptive analysis of the research dimensions, variables and correlation coefficients

	Mean	Std. Deviation	TV	CV	MV	EV	SV	SO	RO	MS	RP	EC	EP
TV	4.02	0.60	1.00										
CV	3.94	0.60	.771**	1.00									
MV	4.13	0.70	.794**	.770**	1.00								
EV	3.87	0.71	.781**	.808**	.771**	1.00							
SV	3.99	0.60	.910**	.911**	.915**	.922**	1.00						
SO	3.87	0.73	.811**	.794**	.845**	.853**	.904**	1.00					
RO	3.98	0.76	.714**	.717**	.824**	.762**	.827**	.867**	1.00				
MS	3.95	0.70	.807**	.778**	.806**	.719**	.849**	.791**	.817**	1.00			
RP	4.01	0.70	.713**	.725**	.633**	.702**	.755**	.673**	.594**	.713**	1.00		
EC	4.11	0.69	.821**	.823**	.812**	.763**	.878**	.814**	.778**	.862**	.771**	1.00	
EP	3.98	0.65	.856**	.849**	.870**	.843**	.934**	.921**	.903**	.926**	.828**	.934**	1.00

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The following results are noted from Table (1):

1. The statistical description of the independent variable of strategic vigilance and its correlation coefficient: The results showed that strategic vigilance obtained an arithmetic mean (3.99) and a standard deviation (0.60) and that it obtained a correlation coefficient of Entrepreneurial performance (EP) (0.93) which is an acceptable positive and moral relationship at a significant level (1 %), As for the dimensions of strategic alertness are as follows:
 - a) The statistical description of the independent variable of strategic vigilance through (technology vigilance (TV)) and its correlation coefficient: the results showed that the technology vigilance (TV) got an arithmetic mean (4.02) and a standard deviation (0.60) and that it got a correlation coefficient of Entrepreneurial performance (EP) (0.856), which is an acceptable positive and moral relationship at a significant level (1%).
 - b) The statistical description of the independent variable of strategic vigilance through (competitive vigilance (CV)) and its correlation coefficient: The results showed that competitive vigilance (CV) got an arithmetic mean (3.94) and a standard deviation (0.60) and that it got a correlation coefficient of

Entrepreneurial performance (EP) (0.846), which is a positive and an acceptable moral relationship at a significant level (1%).

- c) The statistical description of the independent variable of strategic alertness through (marketing vigilance (MV)) and its correlation coefficient: the results showed that the marketing vigilance (MV) got a mean (4.13) and a standard deviation (0.70) and that it got a correlation coefficient of Entrepreneurial performance (EP). 0.87) and it is a positive and moral relationship according to the level of significance acceptable at the level of significance (1%).
 - d) Statistical description of the independent variable of strategic alertness through (environmental alertness (EV)) and its correlation coefficient: The results showed that environmental alertness (EV) got a mean (3.87) and a standard deviation (0.71) and that it got a correlation coefficient of Entrepreneurial performance (EP) (0.84), which is an acceptable positive and moral relationship at a significant level (1%).
2. Statistical description of the dependent variable, Entrepreneurial Performance (EP): The results showed that the entrepreneurial performance (EP) obtained an arithmetic mean (3.98) and a standard deviation (0.65), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.
- a) The results showed that the strategic orientation (SO) obtained an arithmetic mean (3.87) and a standard deviation (0.73), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.
 - b) According to the results, which showed that the resource orientation (RO) got an arithmetic mean (3.98) and a standard deviation (0.76), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.
 - c) According to the results that showed that the management structure (MS) got an arithmetic mean (3.95) and a standard deviation (0.70), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.
 - d) According to the results, which showed that the reward philosophy (RP) had obtained an arithmetic mean (4.01) and a standard deviation (0.70), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.
 - e) According to the results, which showed that the entrepreneurial culture (EC) obtained an arithmetic mean (4.11) and a standard deviation (0.69), and it was higher than the hypothetical mean (3), meaning that it is within the acceptable level.

Second: The global analysis of the research paragraphs: In this paragraph, the consistency of the sample answers on the research paragraphs will be measured by extracting the saturation ratios for each paragraph, as the SMART PLS application provides a level of saturation for each paragraph and a significant level for each of them if the saturation percentage is less than (0.05) Accept the saturation percentage and vice versa will be omitted from the next analysis:

1. The Factor analysis of the strategic vigilance paragraphs: as strategic vigilance consists of four dimensions (technology vigilance (TV), competitive vigilance (CV), marketing vigilance (MV), environmental vigilance (EV)) and each dimension consists of (5) paragraphs, and the figure shows (Saturation ratios and the level of significance for each dimension paragraph. The goal is to measure the consistency of the sample answers:

Figure (2) The Saturation Ratio Coefficient for Strategic vigilance

According to the results shown in the figures (2), it was found that all dimensions of the independent variable strategic alertness (technology alertness (TV), competitive vigilance (CV), marketing vigilance (MV), environmental vigilance (EV)) were at the acceptable level based on the level of morale that was recorded. Ratios less than (5%) means that the scale is characterized by consistency that reflects the clarity of the paragraphs, their affiliation with the objective to be measured, and the adequacy of the sample.

2. A global analysis of the entrepreneurial performance items (EP): as the entrepreneurial performance (EP) consists of five dimensions (strategic orientation (SO), resource orientation (RO), management structure (MS), reward philosophy (RP), entrepreneurial culture (EC)) and each dimension consists of (2-5) paragraphs, and the figure () shows the saturation ratios and the level of significance for each dimension paragraph. The goal is to measure the consistency of the sample answers:

Figure (3) Saturation Ratios Coefficient for Entrepreneurial Performance

According to the results shown in the figures (3), it is found that all dimensions of the dependent variable are entrepreneurial performance (EP) (strategic orientation (SO), resource orientation (RO), management structure (MS), reward philosophy (RP), entrepreneurial culture (EC)). It was at the acceptable level based on the level of significance, which recorded rates less than (5%), meaning that the scale is characterized by consistency that reflects the clarity of the paragraphs, their belonging to the goal to be measured, and the adequacy of the sample.

Third: Testing the research hypotheses: It is assumed in the research methodology that the first hypotheses test the relationship of the effect of strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the second tests the relationship of the effect of strategic vigilance dimensions in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the simple and multiple regression method will be used to test the hypotheses using the program Applied (SMART PLS) in drawing conclusions as the results appear in tables and figures, and both the impact factor and the determination factor will be relied upon in measuring the impact relationship. Either rejecting or accepting the hypothesis will be based on a significant level (0.05):

1. Testing the main hypothesis: This hypothesis stated that there is a positive impact relationship for strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance (EP) at the whole level, meaning that entrepreneurial performance (EP) is a real function of strategic vigilance and that any modification or change in strategic vigilance will be followed by a similar positive change in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship will be tested using simple regression between the two variables, and the figure (4) and table (2) provided by the above program will be used, which displays some of the statistics of the simple regression analysis test, as follows:

Figure (4) factor the influence relationship of strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance (EP)

Table (2) factor the influence relationship of strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance (EP)

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	R ²	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Strategic Vigilance -> Entrepreneurial performance	0.691	0.016	0.48	43.1875	0.000

It is noted from the figure (4) and table (2) the results of the influence relationships recorded by the independent variable of strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance, as the amount of influence was (0.69), which is positive, meaning that any change or increase of one unit in strategic vigilance will lead to an increase in entrepreneurial performance (EP). The relationship is also significant, because the achieved level of morale is (0.000) and it is less than (5%). The quality of the influence relationship has reached a coefficient of determination (R²) (0.48). This means that strategic vigilance explains the amount of (0.48) of the variance in entrepreneurial performance (EP), which is significant according to the level of significance it recorded.

- Sub-hypothesis testing: This hypothesis reported the existence of a positive impact relationship for the dimensions of strategic alertness (technology vigilance (TV), competitive vigilance (CV), marketing vigilance (MV), environmental vigilance (EV)) in entrepreneurial performance (EP) at the whole level. That is, the entrepreneurial performance (EP) is a real function of the dimensions of strategic vigilance, and that any modification or change in the dimensions of strategic vigilance will be followed by a similar positive change in the entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship will be tested using multiple regression between the dimensions of the independent variable and the dependent variable, and the figure will be used. And the table (2) provided by the above program, which shows some statistics of the multiple regression analysis test, as follows:

Figure (5) the influence relationship coefficient for the dimensions of strategic vigilance in entrepreneurial performance (EP).

Table (3) Impact Relationship Coefficient for the Strategic vigilance Dimensions in Entrepreneurial Performance (EP)

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	R ²	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Technology Vigilance -> Entrepreneurial performance	0.268	0.066	0.51	4.039	0.000
Competitive vigilance -> Entrepreneurial performance	0.26	0.062		4.218	0.000
Marketing vigilance -> Entrepreneurial performance	0.354	0.063		5.641	0.000
Environmental vigilance -> Entrepreneurial performance	0.136	0.064		2.137	0.033

It is noticed from the figure (5) and the table (3) that the quality of the influence relationship has reached the coefficient of determination (R²) (0.51). This means that the dimensions of strategic vigilance explain the amount of (0.51) of the variance in the entrepreneurial performance (EP), which is significant according to the level of significance. The results of the influence relationships recorded by (Awakening Technology (TV)) in the entrepreneurial performance, as the amount of the effect was (0.268), which is positive, which means that any change or increase of one unit in (Awakening Technology (TV)) will lead to an increase in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship is significant, because the achieved level of significance is (0.000) and it is less than (5%). According to these results, this hypothesis is accepted. As for the impact relations results

recorded by (competitive vigilance (CV)) in entrepreneurial performance, as the amount of influence was (0.26), which is positive, meaning that any change or increase of one unit in (competitive vigilance (CV)) will lead to an increase in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship is significant, because the achieved level of significance is (0.000) and it is less than (5%). According to these results, this hypothesis is accepted. The results of the influence relationships recorded (MV) in the entrepreneurial performance, as the amount of influence was (0.35), which is positive, which means that any change or increase of one unit in (marketing vigilance (MV)) will lead to an increase in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship is significant, because the achieved level of significance is (0.000) and it is less than (5%). According to these results, this hypothesis is accepted. The results of the influence relationships recorded by (environmental vigilance (EV)) in the entrepreneurial performance, as the amount of the impact was (0.136), which is positive, meaning that any change or increase of one unit in (environmental vigilance (EV)) will lead to an increase in entrepreneurial performance (EP), and the relationship is significant, because the achieved level of significance is (0.033) and it is less than (5%). According to these results, this hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

1. The departments of the Iraqi General Company of Ur give clear attention to the requirements of strategic vigilance of all kinds.
2. These administrations monitor and follow circumstantial events through the environmental information they receive with weak signals, and they work to assess their dangers and confront them with awareness and attention.
3. The company follows up the movements of other competing companies and identifies their strengths and weaknesses, in order to ensure the company an effective presence in the legitimate competition arena and to achieve discrimination over competitors in serving its customers.
4. The results of the research showed that there is an interaction and complementarity between strategic vigilance and entrepreneurial performance that contributed to making the company's management always ready to face unstable environmental conditions and their sudden events as strategic vigilance.

Recommendations

1. It is necessary for the company to adopt a culture of strategic vigilance because of its great importance, especially after the Iraqi markets were opened up to international competition.
2. The company must use a modern information system with advanced technologies capable of collecting data related to customers and updating them continuously to support decision-makers with information that enhances the state of alertness, caution and attention to them and interpreting weak signals coming from the environment at all times with high accuracy.
3. It is necessary for the senior management to implement vigilance and activate its activities on a permanent basis and to conduct courses for managers that include programs of methods and methods of strategic alertness.

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